

Parental Counseling, Knowledge, Practice, Prevalence, and Determinants of Sexual Risk Behaviors Among Students Attending Selected Tertiary Institutions in Kanifing, The Gambia

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Abstract

Sexual risk behaviors (SRBs) are common practices worldwide and they are the major determinants for contracting sexually transmitted diseases such as Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV), unintended pregnancy, abortion, academic interruption, psychological trauma, social stigma, and death among young adults and students. The aim of this research was to study parental counseling, knowledge, practice, prevalence, and determinants of SRBs among students in selected tertiary institutions in Kanifing, The Gambia. This quantitative study supplemented with qualitative assessment was conducted in four purposely selected tertiary institutions in Kanifing, The Gambia. 272 students (14 were randomly selected), aged between 18 and 25 participated and anonymously responded to pre-test self-administered questionnaires. Bivariate analysis was used to describe the dependent and the independent variables, while multivariate analysis was used to determine the correlation between the dependent and the independent variables using Chi-square and Fisher exact statistics. Thematic analysis was used for data analysis. The mean age of the students was 21.8 ± 2.4 years, 72.8% were females, 52.9% have once been counseled on sex-related matters by their parents, 30.1% have never had sex at mean debut age of 18 years, and 16.9% have multiple sexual partners. There was no statistically significant association between parental counseling and SRBs. Among the study participants who have had sex, SRBs like multiple sexual partners were recorded among 56.1%, and sex for reward in 23.2%. There was a low knowledge of SRBs among 49.0% of the study participants. Among the SRBs analyzed, only sexual debut age was statistically associated with SRB knowledge, and higher SRB knowledge correlated with late sexual debut. Thematic analysis generated four themes (forms of SRBs; motivations; fears and worries; and positive influences) and two theories (Theory 1 – Motivations such as sexual urge, curiosity, infatuation, and poor sex education encouraged the study participants to engage in SRBs; and Theory 2 – Fear of sexually transmitted infections (STIs) and unintended pregnancies, worry of female genital mutilation (FGM), and positive influences of youth organizations limited the intense engagement of some study participants in SRBs). Effective sex education to young people by their

More Information

How to cite this article: Anaetor ISC, Ikwuka AO, Udeh FC. Parental Counseling, Knowledge, Practice, Prevalence, and Determinants of Sexual Risk Behaviors Among Students Attending Selected Tertiary Institutions in Kanifing, The Gambia. *Eur J Med Health Res*, 2025;3(2):38-53.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2025.3(2).04

Keywords:

Determinants,
Knowledge,
Multiple Sexual Partners,
Parental Counseling,
Practice,
Prevalence,
Sex for Reward,
Sexual Risk Behaviors,
Students,
Tertiary Education,
The Gambia,
Thematic Analysis,
Transactional Sex.

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parents in a friendly and relaxed atmosphere is essential in reducing SRBs. Providing young people with their basic needs is very important in preventing SRBs.

Introduction

Sexual Risk Behaviors (SRBs) also referred to as Risky Sexual Behaviors, are identified as modes of acquiring or events that elevate the chances of contracting sexually transmitted infections (STIs) such as Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV), gonorrhea, chlamydia, syphilis, etc., and unintended pregnancies [7]. Young adults between 20-24 years of age, followed by teenagers between 15-19 years of age account for the highest number out of the 333 million new cases of STIs occurring yearly [67]. Recently, the World Health Organization (WHO) reported that over 1 million curable STIs are acquired daily globally among individuals aged between 15–49 years [68].

The age range for young adults varies depending on the context. However, ages 18-22 or 18-25 years were defined by the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) as the appropriate age bracket for young adulthood [53]. The period of young adulthood is associated with dramatic changes in basic thinking structures in the brain. In our present world, young adults believe they are full-grown adults, can live as they please and take whatever decision that pleases them. This notion makes them live recklessly, and get involved in risky sexual behaviors that endanger their lives.

Young adults are also prone to various metabolic disorders e.g. diabetes mellitus. In 2021, the International Diabetes Federation (IDF) estimated that sub-Saharan Africa had almost 24 million adults aged 20-79 years who were living with diabetes mellitus with a regional prevalence of 4.5% [30]. Metabolic disorders e.g. hypertension, adiposity (obesity), diabetes mellitus, and dyslipidemia collectively known as Metabolic Syndrome Diseases (MSDs) are interrelated diseases which have very high morbidity and mortality rates [10, 11, 13, 28, 30, 58]. Different studies have also shown that hypertension, adiposity (obesity), diabetes mellitus, and dyslipidemia, as well as asymptomatic hyperuricemia, activation of systemic immune inflammatory processes, and fibrogenesis can lead to kidney damage [14, 15, 18, 19, 20, 25, 27, 29, 59, 60, 61, 62, 66].

Moreover, SRBs are initiated predominantly by the abuse of substances such as alcohol and drugs [49, 50], easy access to pornographic contents, immoral social gatherings and networks, and musical videos illustrating nudity [5]. In some developing societies, including those in The Gambia, socio-cultural norms conventionally hold on due to fear that giving young people comprehensive sexual information will encourage sexual activity, thus making it difficult to

provide optimal and exhaustive sexual information to young people. This idea has been reported to pay off as young adults or adolescents who live with any or both of their parents are less likely to have an early sexual debut [38].

Numerous studies have shown that many young people lack knowledge of the triggers for SRBs [42]. To combat this, interventions have been adopted globally in response to the high prevalence of SRBs, particularly among young people, to increase their awareness to enhance the adoption of safer sexual practices, and to avoid the implications of SRBs. However, these programs fail to target parents who are key stakeholders in enhancing young people's protection against SRBs.

In The Gambia, efforts have been made to increase young people's awareness of SRBs through mainly awareness creation to promote safer sexual behavior [55]. The extent to which awareness efforts from government and partners (including the United Nations (UN) agencies, Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs), and Civil Society Organizations (CSOs)) are directed particularly to groups practicing SRBs is equally not very clear in The Gambia. Nonetheless, such interventions are not very effective in reducing SRBs among young people [51]. The ineffectiveness of the programs was associated with not only a low understanding of triggers and risks, but also failure to initiate focus on the parental protective role and weak communication with their children on sexual and reproductive health issues [52].

The extent of parental counseling in the students, the extent to which students in tertiary institutions in The Gambia know and engage in SRBs, prevalence of SRBs, and determinants or triggers of SRBs among them, are not well known. Hence, the need to conduct this study.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

This study was conducted in Kanifing Municipal Council (KMC) which is one of the seven administrative areas in The Gambia: two municipalities (Banjul and Kanifing) and five regions (West Coast, Lower River, Upper River, North Bank, and Central River). The KMC is where diverse schools are concentrated [54], and the students studying in these schools come from within and outside the KMC communities.

Study Design

This study is a cross-sectional descriptive study using quantitative and qualitative methods to assess SRBs among students in tertiary institutions in KMC, The Gambia.

Study Population

The target population included all students aged 18-25 years in the purposely selected tertiary institutions in the KMC. The selected institutions were the American International University West Africa (AIUWA), University of The Gambia (UTG) Kanifing Campus, Management Development Institute (MDI), and The Gambia Tourism and Hospitality Institute (GTHI). These tertiary institutions were purposely selected in order to capture all diversified areas of learning provided in these tertiary institutions.

Sample Size

Cochrane formula for determining the sample size for cross-sectional studies was employed [32, 33, 45, 46, 47, 48, 56]:

$$n = \frac{Z^2 PQ}{d^2} \tag{1}$$

Where:

n = sample size

Z = standard normal variate usually set at 1.96 which corresponds to a 95% confidence level

P = proportion in population based on previous studies = 23% or 0.23 [9]

Q = 1 – d = 1 – 0.23 = 0.77

d = degree of accuracy desired (absolute precision), which is 5.0% (0.05)

$$n = \frac{1.96^2 \times 0.23 \times 0.77}{0.05^2} = 272$$

Inclusion Criteria

- Students who were between 18 and 25 years, the age bracket for young adults [53] were included.
- Students with >2 months to graduate and readily available.
- Duly registered students in the selected tertiary institutions.
- Students who voluntarily consented to participate in the study without any financial benefits.

Exclusion Criteria

- Students who were 17 years and below or 26 years and above were excluded.
- Students with <2 months to graduate.
- Non-duly registered students in the selected tertiary institutions.
- Students who did not voluntarily consent to participate in the study without any financial benefits.

Sampling Techniques

A multistage sampling technique was employed. All the departments, referred to as strata, were represented, just as the years of study (clusters) in each department. A total of 272 students were systematically selected from each cluster depending on probability proportionate to the relative size of the individual cluster. Clusters with few students were merged.

A random sampling technique was used for the qualitative assessment. A similar study in terms of study population and size used 20 interviewees. To ensure that a range of gender identity and diversity were represented, 14 (5% of the sample size) interviewees were randomly selected for every tenth participant, comprising of 4 males and 10 females, out of which three of the interviewees were married.

Data Collection

A set of anonymously pre-tested, well structured, self-administered questionnaires, and an in-depth interview guide were used for data collection. The questionnaires were written in the English Language and categorized into four sections as follows: Section A for socio-demographic characteristics, Section B focused on parental counseling, Section C captured data on the practice of SRBs, and Section D dealt with the knowledge of SRBs. The in-depth interview was made of 38 open-ended research questions.

Quantitative Data Collection: All the activities for the quantitative data collection were performed by one of the researchers with the help of two adequately trained research assistants. The questionnaires were administered and collected immediately after completion. All data collected from each study participant were checked for completeness, clarity, and consistency by the collector immediately at the end of each data collection day.

Qualitative Data Collection: Good rapport was established among the selected students for the interviews. In-depth interviews were conducted privately. The interviewees willingly described their experiences and expressed their opinions in their own words.

Reliability and Validity of Study Instruments

All data collection instruments were validated after reviewing relevant literatures and consulting with the experts in the field. The questionnaire and interview questions were reformulated after a pilot test among 15 respondents selected randomly in another similar target population outside the KMC, and the overall Cronbach’s Alpha value obtained was 0.81 indicating a good reliability. In general, a Cronbach’s Alpha value of 0.70 and above is considered acceptable.

The research assistants were excellent at interacting with young people of diverse sexual orientations, and were further trained intensively concerning the study. These steps were taken to ensure the reliability and validity of the research instruments.

Variables

The independent variables were presumed to predict and influence the dependent variables e.g. parental counseling, knowledge, practice, and prevalence of SRBs. The dependent variables relied on the independent variables to occur. These dependent variables include age at first sex (age at sexual debut),

number of past or current sexual partners, condom use during sex, and sex for reward (transactional sex).

Measurement of Study Variables

The knowledge of the study participants on SRBs was scored. The variables under knowledge were selected from the questionnaires based on their magnitude of answering the research questions. Six questions were selected and scored for knowledge level of SRBs. Yes was 1 point and No was 0 point which made the maximum score on knowledge of SRBs to be 6 points. Thus, the decision for quantifying the knowledge of SRBs was set at 0-2 points for low knowledge, 3-4 points for average knowledge, and 5-6 points for high knowledge.

Data Analysis

The quantitative data analysis was performed using SPSS version 22. Bivariate analysis was used for the descriptions of the dependent and the independent variables. Multivariate analysis was used to determine the correlation between the dependent and the independent variables using Chi-square and Fisher exact statistics. Data from the interview were analyzed using thematic analysis. Inductive (data-driven) thematic analysis was employed [3]. The qualitative data collected were carefully read for familiarization, summarized in bullets, and the researchers’ initial ideas on the responses were documented. Next was harmonizing the data into codes, and potential themes. Sub-themes were generated from the codes. The themes and sub-themes were refined for the final listing. Lastly, a report was made.

Ethical Considerations

This research initiative was voluntary, with permissions to conduct the study obtained from the School of Medicine and Allied Health Sciences Research and Scientific Committee of UTG, the Joint National Institute for Medical Research Council (MRC) Unit of The Gambia, and The Gambian Government Ethics Committee. Permissions to conduct the study were also obtained from the respective administrations of the institutions. With the names of the participants withheld, they verbally consented and appropriately filled in the consent form and consented to partake in the research without any financial benefits. A proper briefing of the whole research process was given to every study participant, and every data obtained from each of them was held confidential. The study participants retained full autonomy throughout the research process and had the unequivocal right to withdraw within 2 weeks of taking part in the research without any explanation or consequence.

Results

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Characteristics of the Study Participants

Variable	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age (Years)		
18-19	30	11.0
20-21	103	37.9
22-23	90	33.1
24-25	49	18.0
Mean age = 21.8±2.4 years		
Gender		
Male	74	27.2
Female	198	72.8
Nationality		
Gambian	265	97.4
Non-Gambian	7	2.6
Tribe		
Fula	62	22.8
Jola	32	11.8
Mandinka	109	40.1
Serahuli	7	2.6
Serer	16	5.9
Wolof	44	16.2
Marital Status		
Divorced	4	1.5
Married	17	6.2
Single	250	91.9
Widowed	1	0.4
Who do you currently live with?		
Your mother	75	27.6
Your father	25	9.2
Both your mother and father	121	44.5
Your grandmother	13	4.8
Your grandfather	2	0.7
Aunt	19	7.0
Uncle	5	1.8
Sibling	12	4.4

Table 1 illustrates the socio-demographic characteristics of the study participants. The age range of the study participants was clustered between 20-23 years (71.0%), 18-19 years were the least group (11.0%), and the mean age of the study participants was 21.8±2.4 years. Females (72.8%) were more than the males (27.2%). Almost all were Gambian (97.4%), and single (91.9%).

Table 2: Statistical Illustration of Parental Counseling among the Study Participants

Variable	n	%	Statistic Test	p-value
1. Has any of your parents/guardians counseled you on sex?			†	0.424
Yes	144	52.9		
No	128	47.1		
If yes, how often?				
Once	20	13.9		
Twice	11	7.6		
More than twice	113	78.5		
2. If yes, what counseling approach(es) was/were used?			R ²	0.025
Beat you	47	32.6		
Talk to you harshly	139	96.5		
Give out punishment to you	90	62.5		
Fail to provide your needs when they can	40	27.8		
Neglect you physically or emotionally	43	29.9		
3. Does any of your parents/guardians monitor your relationship with friends?				
Yes	205	75.5		
No	67	24.5		

Note: n = Frequency; % = Percentage

Table 2 shows that a little above average number of the study participants attested that their parents or guardians have counseled them on sex (52.9%), and a large proportion (78.5%) reported having been counseled more than twice. The counseled group reported several ways that they were counseled, out of

which almost all (96.5%) agreed that they were counseled about sex in a harsh tone, and 32.6% agreed that they were beaten. Approximately 75.5% of all the study participants were strictly monitored by their parents or guardians. However, 47.1% have never been counseled on sex.

Table 3: Knowledge of Sexual Risk Behaviors (SRBs) among the Study Participants

Variable	n	%
Have you heard of the term SRBs?*		
Yes	75	26.8
No	197	73.2
Select one or multiple options that describe SRBs.		
a. Unprotected sexual intercourse*	105	38.6
b. Atypical sexual practices like anal sex, oral sex, the use of sex toys, and ingestion of partner’s ejaculates and other body fluids	128	47.1
c. Sex after the use of illicit drugs or alcohol abuse	71	26.1
d. Sex with multiple sexual partners or strangers*	143	52.6
e. Premarital sexual act	119	43.8
Select multiple options that describe the consequences of SRBs.		
a. Sexually transmitted infections (STIs)*	114	41.9
b. Unintended pregnancy	132	48.5
c. Abortion	70	25.7
d. Academic interruption	55	20.2
e. Psychological trauma	89	32.7
f. Social stigma	74	27.2
g. Death	54	19.9
Do you think having multiple sexual partners increases the risk of STIs?		
Yes	212	77.9
No	60	22.1
Does early sexual debut (starting sexual activity at a young age) increase the risk of sexual health problems?		
Yes	164	60.3

No	108	39.7
Is it safe to rely solely on a partner’s word about their STI status without testing?		
Yes	76	27.9
No	196	72.1
Do you think regular STI testing is necessary for sexually active individuals?		
Yes	212	77.9
No	60	22.1
Do you know how to protect yourself from contractingSTIs?*		
Yes	209	76.8
No	73	23.2
If ‘yes’ is your response to question 8, then, what is the best way of preventing STIs?		
a. Abstinence*	116	55.5
b. Sticking to one STI-free partner	29	13.9
c. By use of condoms	46	22.0
d. Knowing your partner’s health status	13	6.2
e. Other(s)	5	2.4

Note: n = Frequency; % = Percentage; * = selected items for overall knowledge of SRBs

Approximately 73.2% of the study participants have not heard about SRBs as illustrated in Table 3. In describing SRBs, 38.6% agreed that engaging in unprotected sexual intercourse is an SRB, 47.1% reported that atypical sexual practices were SRBs, 26.1% agreed that sex after illicit drugs or alcohol abuse is an SRB, 52.6% agreed that sex with multiple sexual partners or strangers is an SRB, while 43.8% highlighted that premarital sexual act is an SRB. The participants highlighted the consequences of SRBs in the following order: STIs (41.9%), unintended pregnancy (48.5%), abortion (25.7%), academic interruption (20.2%), psychological trauma (32.7%), social stigma (27.2%), and death (19.9%).

The majority of the study participants (77.9%) believed that having multiple sexual partners increases the risk

of STIs. In addition, 60.3% of the study participants believed that early sexual debut increases the risk of sexual health problems. 72.1% of the study participants reported that it is not safe to rely solely on a partner’s word about their STI status without testing. Regular STI testing was supported by 77.9% to be necessary for sexually active individuals. Notably, 23.2% of the study participants do not know how to protect themselves from STIs. However, of those who know how to protect themselves from STIs (76.8%), the majority of them (55.5%) agreed that abstinence is the best way of preventing the contraction of STIs, while others agreed that the use of condoms (22.0%), sticking to one STI-free partner (13.9%), and knowing your partner’s health status (6.2%) were the best methods.

Table 4: Practice of Sexual Risk Behaviors (SRBs) among the Study Participants

Variable	Gender					
	Male		Female		Total	
	n	(%)	n	(%)	n	(%)
1. Have you ever had sexual intercourse?						
Yes	46	61.3	36	18.3	82	30.1
No	29	38.7	161	81.7	190	69.9
2. At what age did you have sex for the first time?						
≤14 years	6	13.3	4	11.1	10	12.2
15-17 years	12	26.7	7	19.4	19	23.2
18-20 years	17	37.9	16	44.5	33	40.3
≥21 years	11	24.4	9	25.0	20	24.4
Mean age = 18 years						
3. How old was/were your 1st sexual partner(s)?						
6 years	1	2.2	-	-	1	1.2
7-29 years	45	97.8	30	83.3	75	91.5
30-52 years	-	-	6	16.7	6	7.3
Mean age = 23 years						

4. Are you still in a relationship with this person?						
Yes	20	43.5	21	58.3	41	50.0
No	26	56.5	15	41.7	41	50.0
5. Apart from this person, have you had sexual intercourse with any other person?						
Yes	25	54.3	11	30.6	36	43.9
No	21	45.7	25	69.4	46	56.1
6. How old was/were your other sexual partners? (n=35)						
≤17years (adolescents)	1	4.0	-	-	1	2.9
18-25 years (young adults)	20	80.0	8	80.0	28	80.0
>25 years (adults)	4	16.0	2	20.0	6	17.1
Mean age = 22 years						
7. Number of sexual partners in your lifetime						
1	15	32.6	21	58.3	36	43.9
2-5	22	47.8	13	36.1	35	42.7
6-9	9	19.6	2	5.6	11	13.4
8. Have you ever paid anyone in exchange for having sexual intercourse?						
Yes	10	21.7	-	-	10	12.2
No	36	78.3	36	100.0	72	87.8
9. In the last 12 months, were you paid by anyone or have you ever paid anyone in exchange for sexual intercourse?						
Yes	3	6.5	-	-	3	5.7
No	43	93.5	36	100.0	79	96.3
10. Have you ever had sex with anyone for a reward?						
Yes	11	23.9	8	22.2	19	23.2
No	35	76.1	28	77.8	63	76.8
11. The reward/favor was for (n=19)						
For money	2	40.0	4	33.3	6	31.6
Mobile phone	3	60.0	7	58.4	10	52.6
Any other help	-	-	3	8.3	3	15.8

Note: n = Frequency; % = Percentage

Table 4 reveals that 30.1% of the study participants have had sexual intercourse, with the majority (61.3%) being males and 18.3% were females. For those who have had sexual intercourse, 12.2% had the first sex at age 14 years or earlier. 43.5% of the males and 58.3% of the females who were sexually active reported continuity of their relationships with their first sexual partner. 54.3% of the males and 30.6% of the females

have had sexual intercourse with another partner with the mean age of these other partners being 22 years. No female agreed to have paid anyone in exchange for having sexual intercourse, but 21.7% of the males agreed to have paid for sex. In addition, among those who have had sexual intercourse, some agreed to have had sex for reward or favor such as money (31.6%), mobile phone (52.6%), and any other help (15.8%).

Table 5: Association between Parental Counseling and the Dependent Variables

Variable	Has any of your parents/guardians advised you on sex				p-value
	Yes		No		
	n	%	n	%	
	144	52.9	128	47.1	0.424
Number of partners					0.903
1	19	23.2	17	20.7	
2-5	17	20.7	18	22.0	
6-9	5	6.1	6	7.3	
Age of first partner (years)					0.676
≤6	0	0	1	1.2	
7-29	37	45.1	38	46.3	
30-52	2	2.4	4	4.8	

Age of second partner (years)					0.126
≤17	1	2.9	0	0	
18–29	12	34.3	16	45.7	
30–41	5	14.3	1	2.9	
Do you engage in sex for a reward or favor?					0.588
Yes	24	9.0	43	16.0	
No	114	42.0	91	33.0	
Do you use condoms during sex?					0.145
Yes	10	12.2	10	12.2	
No	32	39.0	30	36.6	

Note: *n* = Frequency; % = Percentage

Table 5 shows no statistically significant association between parental counseling and the dependent variables of SRBs among the study participants. Even though parental counseling was low (52.9%), the table reflected that among the study participants whom their parents or guardians have counseled on sex, a majority

have had multiple sexual partners. However, most of them have never engaged in sex for a reward or favor. Low condom use was observed in those who have been counseled on sex as well as in those who have not been counseled on sex.

Table 6: Association between Knowledge of SRBs (Independent Variables) and the Dependent Variables among the Study Participants

Variable	Knowledge Level of SRBs						p-value
	Low		Average		High		
Overall knowledge score	49.0%		37.0%		14.0%		
	<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%	
Age of first partner (years)							0.72
≤6	2	2.4	0	0	0	0	
7–29	39	47.6	24	29.3	10	12.2	
30–52	5	6.1	2	2.4	0	0	
Age of second partner (years)							0.60
≤17	0	0	1	2.8	0	0	
18–29	14	38.9	10	27.8	5	13.8	
30–41	4	11.1	2	5.6	0	0	
Age at first sex (years)							0.01
≤8	0	0	0	0	1	1.2	
9–14	6	7.3	3	3.7	0	0	
15–20	32	39.0	17	20.7	3	3.7	
21–25	8	9.6	6	7.3	6	7.3	
Do you engage in sex for a reward?							0.80
Yes	9	11.0	5	6.1	5	6.1	
No	34	41.5	22	26.8	7	8.5	
Do you use condoms during sex?							0.39
Yes	32	39.0	16	19.5	7	8.5	
No	11	13.4	10	12.2	6	7.3	

Note: *n* = Frequency; % = Percentage

Table 6 shows that the majority of the students (49.0%) have low knowledge of SRBs. There is no statistically significant association ($p > 0.05$) between knowledge of SRBs and age of first partner, age of second partner, sex for reward, and use of condom. However, a statistically significant association was found between knowledge of SRBs and age at first sex ($p = 0.01$).

Using the six selected questions as the yardstick to determine the knowledge level of SRBs, Figure 1 shows that the overall knowledge level of SRBs was low for 49.0% of the study participants, average for 37.0% of them, and high for only 14.0% of them. Inferably, 51.0% of the study participants can be said to be aware of SRBs and its consequences.

Figure 1: Knowledge of SRBs among the Study Participants

Figure 2: Summary of Themes and Codes on the Practice of SRBs among the Study Participants

This thematic analysis generated four themes and two theories as described as follows:

Thematic Analysis of the Interview Data on Knowledge and Practice of SRBs among the Study Participants

Theme 1: Forms of SRBs

It was observed that majority of the interviewed female had never initiated penetrative sexual intercourse, although some have engaged in oral sex and having romance with their boyfriends. One of them expressed:

“I have a boyfriend. We do have all sorts of romance but no penetrative sex.” - (from a 22-year-old female study participant)

“My girlfriend does not like me using condoms and I wouldn’t want to father another man’s child because some of these girls are too wild.” - (from a 24-year-old male study participant)

Most sexually active males complained that some girls do not like them to use condoms. One of the boys lamented that he had never used a condom. Another male study participant reported that his girlfriend dislikes condoms and he does not want to be implicated in another man’s sexual act. This reason buttresses the practice of multiple sexual partners (MSPs) among the students in The Gambia as identified in the quantitative

data. Hatred for condoms exposes sexually active individuals to STIs and unintended pregnancy which are major consequences of SRBs.

Theme 2: Motivations

The interviews show that most of the young males pointed out that curiosity and the urge to have sex were their motivations for having sex at first, whilst the females expressed that love and infatuation were their main motivations.

"The urge to satisfy my sexual drive pushed me to experience sex. I enjoyed my first sexual experience and wanted more." - (from a 19-year-old male study participant)

"I truly love my boyfriend and I love to do many sexual acts with him." - (from a 20-year-old female study participant)

"Parents, like my parents, don't teach their children sex education." - (from a 22-year-old female study participant)

The interviews highlighted the influence of the lack of sex education provided by parents/guardians. This gap and lack of awareness left some study participants to engage in SRBs recklessly due to their limited knowledge and preparedness for safe sexual practices.

Theme 3: Fears and worries

During the interview on fears and worries after sexual intercourse among those who have had sexual intercourse, unintended pregnancy was quite widely expressed. As they expressed their fears and worries about engaging in SRBs, the females feared getting pregnant while the males feared getting their girlfriends pregnant. They also fear contracting STIs such as HIV or being blamed for infecting their partner.

"The very first day I had sex, I was very worried about impregnating a girl at this my age. How will I face my mother if this girl gets pregnant? I lost appetite for some time." - (from a 21-year-old male study participant)

"I am afraid to father a child at this age. Also, I'm worried that my girlfriend might get pregnant from another man and accuse me of being responsible." - (from a 25-year-old male study participant)

Genetic testing also known as DNA testing can be used to determine a child's parentage (genetic mother and genetic father) [24]. Notably, a female was worried about the nature of her genitalia due to female genital mutilation (FGM) during circumcision. She exposed that female circumcision is possibly still practiced in The Gambia. Even as FGM has restricted her from engaging in sexual intercourse and deriving pleasure from sex, the trauma of having undergone FGM affects her mental health as observed from her voice, and expression.

"I had circumcision and also had stitches that prevent any penetration. I have not had sexual

intercourse. But I think and will not encourage anybody to do her child such a thing, because I see it as putting pain on women." (from a 22-year-old female study participant)

When asked about the preventive measures they use against their worries, it was found that the majority use withdrawal methods, and some of their girlfriends are on contraceptive pills and injections. Even though few use condoms, they use them mainly to prevent pregnancy rather than preventing HIV and other STIs. However, a male study participant confirmed that HIV was his main worry.

"I always use condoms each time I am having sex with my girlfriend." - (from a 19-year-old male study participant)

Theme 4: Positive influences

The male study participants who are consistent in using condoms associated this precautionary measure with membership in youth organizations. It was reported that the group members are trained on SRBs and taught preventive measures, with a keen attention on abstinence. This group is very beneficial and would be encouraged as many study participants do not have sufficient knowledge of SRBs, and do not know that abstinence is the best preventive measure for STIs, and unintended pregnancy.

"I am a member of The Voice of Gam Youth Corp, NSG. There, we are taught comprehensively about SRBs, and their consequences. I observed that most youths do not know how to protect themselves against STIs." - (from a 23-year-old male study participant)

Theory 1: Motivations like curiosity, sexual urge, love and infatuation, and limited sex education from parents/guardians encourage the study participants to engage in SRBs.

Theory 2: The fear of unintended pregnancies and STIs, worry about FGM, and positive influences of youth organizations limit the engagement of some study participants in SRBs.

Discussion

This current study provides some insights into parental counseling, knowledge, practice, prevalence, and determinants of sexual risk behaviors (SRBs) among students in selected tertiary institutions in Kanifing, The Gambia.

The findings in this current study show that most of the students in the tertiary institutions were between 20-23 years, and approximately one-tenth were between 18-19 years. Since the students were selected irrespective of their class, this result signifies that most of the students in Gambian tertiary institutions are admitted in their late teenage years and early 20s. As females accounted for more than two-thirds of the sample size in this current study, the higher number of females shows that they are more enrolled for

academic studies. This implies that Gambian women are more enrolled in schools than their men, supporting the findings of other studies [34, 56].

Participants from the Mandinka tribe were the most numerous, suggesting their dominance within the Kanifing Municipal Council (KMC) and their academic enrollment, which agrees with the report from another study [38]. It should be pointed out that even though a small number of the study participants were non-Gambians, yet they belong to tribes commonly found in The Gambia as these non-Gambians came from neighboring countries to The Gambia such as Senegal, Guinea (Conakry). Most of the study participants were single and living with both parents. A simple explanation for this is the mean age of 21.8 years which is the age most African young adults are still focused on tertiary education or apprenticeship, and still being sponsored by their parents.

In contrast to some previous studies which stated that young people who live with their parents who strictly monitor their activities and know their whereabouts are significantly less likely to initiate sexual intercourse, unlike those living away from their parents without any restriction [38, 57], the results of this current study show that parental counseling had no statistically significant association with SRBs. This implies that SRBs engaged in by young adults were not entirely due to poor parental counseling on sexuality or lack of strict monitoring. Nonetheless, the qualitative analysis reported that some study participants complained about not being trained on sexuality by their parents. The statistical finding on parental counseling is consistent with the report of a different study [39], and the practice of SRBs could be a result of the gap in the approach to effective sex education. This gap needs to be addressed for more parent-child connection which hopefully can reduce SRBs significantly. Most young people seek and get sex education from friends and peer groups both in school and at home, and various social media platforms have also been reported to expose many young people to sex, and pornography.

Similar to the findings of other studies where adolescents attending secondary schools agreed to be influenced by peer pressure, and a sibling using marijuana [49, 50], which supports further the roles of friends, family, and social media in influencing young adults to engage in societal vices. The use of marijuana has been associated with increased oxidative stress. Linked with the induction of oxidative stress are major free radicals. Among these major free radicals, superoxide anion, hydroxyl radical, and hydroperoxyl radical are of physiological significance. Non-radical of physiological significance is hydrogen peroxide [23]. Many parents at home, even mothers are hesitant to teach their teenage children sex education, cautious against the dangers of experimenting with sex at a

younger age, sensitizing and warning them about the potential consequences of exposure to sexually transmitted diseases, especially teaching the female children about menstruation.

This current study reported that approximately one-third (30.1%) of the study participants have had sexual intercourse, some debuting as early as 14 years or less (12.2%). This finding is consistent with the findings of the National Aids Secretariat (NAS) of The Gambia in 2012 [44], The Gambia Bureau of Statistics (GBoS) where sex before age 15 among young Gambian women was reported [54], another study which reported 14.7 years as the sexual debut age among Gambian girls [38], and another report where 50.0% of young people in KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa were already sexually active by the age of 16 years [8]. However, the prevalence of sexual activities in this current study (30.1%) is lower than the 67.65% reported in another study [37]. The early sexual debut can be attributed to low self-control. Single young males initiate sexual activities earlier than their female counterparts, further emphasizing the fact that males have lower self-control compared to females.

Having multiple sexual partners (MSPs) is one of the means of HIV spread [43]. This current study found that the practice of MSPs was prevalent as most of the study participants who have had sex agreed to having more than one sexual partner since their sexual debut. In relation to the total sample size, 16.9% have had multiple sexual partners. The practice of MSPs could be related to the dominant polygamy in The Gambia, which is further supported by Islam, the dominant religion. These findings correlate with the findings from other studies in Ghana [36], England [2], the United States of America [4], and Nigeria [1] where the prevalence rates of MSPs were significant. The prevalence rate of MSPs reported in this current study is lesser than the 80.0% prevalence rate among 15–49 year-old adults previously recorded by the National Aids Secretariat (NAS) of The Gambia in 2012 [44], but higher than the 1.1% prevalence rate among 15–49 year-old women reported in another study by the GBoS also in 2012 [54]. The reports of NAS, The Gambia in 2012, and GBoS also in 2012 were made over a decade ago. Therefore, the report of this current study gives an updated insight into the prevalence of MSPs among Gambian young adults.

Transactional sex is a global health menace, and the items received in exchange for sex vary [6, 41]. Poverty and lack of basic needs constrain some young people to engage in sex for rewards or favors which could be money, mobile phones, food, clothes, trips, etc. Sex for reward or transactional sex is one of the SRBs that contribute to increasing the prevalence of HIV infection and other STIs. This current study finds that 19 (7.0%) of the sexually active participants have been rewarded

in exchange for sex previously, and 3 (1.1%) have been paid or have paid for sex in the last twelve months. This report is similar to the report of another study which reported a 30.0% incidence of sex for money or other gratification among sexually active female university students [1]. Another study reported sex for reward among 12–19 year-olds in Burkina Faso, Ghana, Malawi, and Uganda but with an average incidence of 66.5% among females and 20.6% among males who had sex in the last 12 months in the four countries [41]. This current study highlights that mobile phone was the most sought reward, followed by money, indicating the need for parents to improve in fending for their children, particularly the female child.

Quantitative data shows that in concordance with another study [40], the outcome of this study on the knowledge of SRBs shows that a substantial number of young people have not heard of sexual risk behaviors, and therefore, are not sufficiently informed about SRBs and their implications. As observed in their response to the questionnaire, the term “Sexual Risk Behavior” sounded strange to most of the study participants even as they engaged in one or multiple forms of SRBs. A fraction of the study participants know the description and consequences of SRBs, and the best method of preventing STIs. Their description of SRBs majored on sex with MSPs. The most familiar consequences of SRBs to the study participants were unintended pregnancy and STIs. Less than half of them know that abstinence is the best method to prevent STIs. Nevertheless, the quantitative data illustrated that about half of the study participants know about SRBs, a finding lower than the 75.9% awareness rate reported in a different study [35]. These findings on the knowledge of SRBs can be related to poor sex education from parents, guardians, schools, and the society.

Qualitative analysis showed that a few interviewees demonstrated sufficient knowledge of SRBs. The few that are familiar with SRBs had the advantage of having been taught SRBs in youth empowerment and training groups they belong. This outlines the benefit of membership in these groups in curbing youthful exuberances. The majority believed that abstinence is mainly the way to reduce the chance of contracting STIs. In addition to the fear of STIs and unwanted pregnancy, this current study further identified that female genital mutilation (FGM) is another factor limiting SRBs among girls as reported by an interviewee. This information gives an insight into the practice of FGM within the study area, thus requiring an urgent intervention.

Nevertheless, as young adults are also prone to various metabolic disorders such as adiposity (obesity), diabetes mellitus, etc., there is an important need for new and effective treatment options in patients with metabolic disorders. Obesity has been reported to be a

risk factor for multiple myeloma, and non-Hodgkin lymphoma [22]. Sodium-Glucose Linked Transporter 2 (SGLT-2) inhibitors e.g. Dapagliflozin [12, 16, 17, 26, 31, 63, 64, 65], and Glucagon-like Peptide 1 Receptor Agonists (GLP-1 RAs) e.g. Liraglutide [21] have been found to improve the efficacy of treatment and clinical course of metabolic disorders such as type 2 diabetes mellitus and hypertension, in patients with both metabolic disorders.

Notwithstanding the above discussion, there could be other factors that affect sexual behavior in young adults. Therefore, there is a need for continued research to improve our understanding of the determinants driving SRBs in young adults. This will contribute immensely to the mapping out of strategies for improving healthy sexual behaviors in young adults.

Conclusion

The adoption of safer sexual practices among young adults appears to be slow. Knowledge of SRBs is insufficient in young adults attending tertiary institutions in Kanifing, The Gambia. This may adversely increase the prevalence of HIV and other STIs in the population. Some female study participants have not yet had a penetrative sexual intercourse, but yet indulge in oral sex, and all manners of romance with their boyfriends. Therefore, all relevant stakeholders must redesign, develop, implement, and optimize SRB intervention programs that will target young adults. This will complement the capacity of parents and guardians in effective parenting, and communication skills and will ultimately reduce SRBs among young adults. FGM intervention programs need speedy improvement in order to mitigate the practice effectively as a case of FGM was recorded in this current study.

Acknowledgments

The authors express their gratitude to everyone who contributed in one way or the other to make this research a success. The authors are also grateful to all the students who participated in this research for their cooperation and support, which are highly appreciated.

Conflict of Interest

The authors hereby declare that they do not have any possible conflicts of interest.

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